

The initial COREnect ecosystems

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One of the main objectives of the COREnect project is to identify and engage the **stakeholders that shall potentially become involved in the "European core technologies for future connectivity systems", in short, the COREnect community.** A second objective is to identify the **external communities that shall benefit from the results obtained and released by this COREnect community, i.e., the COREnect technologies' users.**

During the first six months of the project, the initial engagement activities focused on identifying and starting to engage the most relevant stakeholders and start building the **COREnect community.** The first stage of identification of the external communities was performed as well. Particular attention was paid to both the telecommunications and the ECS communities and "complementary" ecosystems in domains such as AI, IoT, cloud... and vertical sectors.

Considering the complexity and broad scope of those two communities, the analysis was split into two parts. On the one hand, the **COREnect provisioning ecosystem** represents the COREnect community, i.e., the stakeholders involved in developing the COREnect-related technologies; on the other hand, the **COREnect use-case ecosystem**, gathering the users of COREnect technologies.

The outcome of this initial analysis is represented in two "stakeholder pictures". Figure 1 shows the preliminary representation of the COREnect provisioning ecosystem.

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* SMEs and large companies are stakeholders of this category and in all its sub-groups

Figure 1: initial COREnect provisioning ecosystem stakeholder picture (the COREnect community)

All the details of the initial analysis may be found in COREnect **Deliverable 4.1 "Initial report on community building and outreach strategy"**. Identification and engagement of the COREnect stakeholders will continue further in the upcoming months.